

HIV PREVALENCE IN A RURAL COMMUNITY OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

National sentinel surveys show that Iquita rural community in Nigeria with estimated 15,000 people with persistent high HIV prevalence. This study aimed at determining factors potentially contributing to the spread of HIV in this rural community. We administered structured questionnaire to one individual 15 to 70 years in randomly selected 350 households, and another questionnaire to 50 people living with AIDS receiving treatment at the general hospital. Results show knowledge of transmission was high among respondents 326 (93.1%) said through blood transfusion, and 317(90.6%) unprotected sex. Yet 20.0% said kissing/hugging 14.9% mosquitoes, 10.0% witches and wizards; and 64.6% God's punishment for immorality. About 90% was sexually active with early onset, 26.9% had first sexual experience between 11 to 15 years. Last sexual encounter for 52.9% was with boy or girl friend, and 8.9% concubine and commercial sex worker, nearly 50% had more than one sexual partner; yet many did not like using condom because it was not pleasurable 62.1% males and 24.3% females.

Results from those living with HIV show that 72.0 % of the fifty respondents did not know if other members of their family were infected; 38.0% did not protect their sexual partner, only 24.0% used condom, and 10.0% would not die alone. Hence, despite treatment, counselling, and knowledge of HIV transmission some respondents presumably did not want to protect sexual partners. In conclusion, results suggest numerous factors fuelling the spread of HIV in Iquita, particularly multiple sexual partners, and reluctance to use protective measures. In-depth qualitative research is needed for deeper understanding persistent high HIV prevalence in this community, particularly on the behaviour of those living with HIV.

KEYWORDS: Rural HIV Spread, HIV Prevalence, Community Beliefs and HIV.

INTRODUCTION

The world continues to battle the HIV pandemic along with related social and economic challenges. Strategies applied in developed countries seem to be containing the spread; however, results of efforts in many African countries are daunting. At the end of 2009, an estimated 33.3 million people were infected with HIV globally, 22.5 million (68%) of global total were in Sub-Saharan Africa, and about 2.98 million in Nigeria with second highest after South Africa of people living with HIV in the World (UNAIDS, 2010).

Reports of sentinel survey on 36,427 pregnant women 15 to 49 years who attended antenatal clinics at 160 selected sentinel sites in Nigeria show a national HIV prevalence of 4.1%, ranging 1.0% to 12.7%. Benue 12.7%, Akwa Ibom 10.9%, Bayelsa 9.1%, Anambra 8.7%, Abuja 8.6%, and Plateau 7.7% had the highest rates. The HIV prevalence in the South – South zone was 6.5%, ranging from 4.1% in Delta to 10.9% in Akwa Ibom. Urban prevalence ranged from 4.4% in Delta and 10.8% in Akwa Ibom, while rural prevalence ranged from 1.6% in Cross River and 11.1% in Akwa Ibom. Two rural communities in Akwa Ibom state were in the survey Ikono with 5.8% and Iquita Oron 10.9% prevalence (Federal Ministry of Health 2010).

Similarly, from earlier reports Iquita community had the highest site specific HIV prevalence rate of 14.7% in Nigeria (Federal Ministry of Health 2005). Again, reports from Akwa Ibom State show prevalence rates of 1.4% in 1993, 12.5% in 1999, 10.7% in 2001, 7.2% in 2003, and 8.0% in 2005 (Akwa Ibom State Action Committee on AIDS 2005).

Objectives

This study aimed at determining factors that contribute to the spread of HIV in rural Iquita of Nigeria; and services available for people living with HIV and AIDS.

METHODOLOGY

Iquita is a rural community in Oron Local Government of Akwa Ibom State with estimated population of 15,000 people, a river community and mini-port with commercial fishermen, sailors and international traders. The people largely engage in small scale farming, fishing, trading, canoe/boat making, and water transporting. Iquita had one general hospital established in 1942.

We selected 350 households using systematic random sampling and administered structured questionnaire to one individual per household aged 15 to 70 years, and another questionnaire to 50 people living with HIV receiving treatment at the General Hospital who volunteered to participate in the study. We pretested the questionnaire on 20 randomly selected males and females 15 years to 70 years in Nkemba, another rural community. Results helped to fine tune the Iquita community questionnaire.

The Village Head of Iquita gave approval for entry into the community, and each respondent gave verbal informed consent. The State Ministry of Health approved access to the General Hospital, the Medical Superintendent approved involvement of patients in the study, and each respondent voluntarily participated, gave verbal consent before administration of questionnaire and we did not record names or contact information of respondents. Microsoft Excel 2007 was used for data entry and analysis.

RESULTS FROM COMMUNITY DATA

Demographic information

Out of the 350 respondents, 202 (57.7%) were females and 148 (42.3%) males; 83(23.7%) 20-24 years, 78(22.5%) 15-19 years, 69(19.7%) 25-29, 41(11.7%) 30-34 years. 192(54.8%) were single, and 111(31.7%) married. Over 50% (190) had secondary education, 97(27.7%) tertiary, 33(9.4%) no formal education and 30(8.6%) primary education (table 1). Most 121(34.6%) were students, 89(25.5%) civil servants, 63(18.0%) traders and 40(11.4%) unemployed. Understandably, many 158(45.1%) had no source of income, 65(18.6%) earned N21,000 and above monthly, (N21,000 ÷ by 158, about 133 US dollars or more) 46(13.1%) between N6,000-N1000. Respondents were largely 315(90.0%) Christians and 20(5.7%) Muslims. A good number 47(42.0%) had lived in the community 16 or more years, 67(19.4%) 6-10 years, and most 316(90.3%) were Nigerians and 34(9.7%) foreigners (Table 2).

Knowledge of HIV, and beliefs

Huge proportion 345(98.6%) had heard about HIV and AIDS, and most 331 (94.5%) said HIV was real. Sources of information varied, radio 196 (56.0%), television 92(26.3%) and 80(22.8%) from the health facility. Most 326(93.1%) said HIV/AIDS was transmitted through blood transfusion, 321(91.7%) needle and syringes, 317(90.6%) unprotected sex, 313(89.4%) said sharp objects, 70(20.0%) said kissing/hugging 52(14.9%) mosquitoes, 35(10.0%) witches and wizards (Table 3).

Many 226 (64.6%) believed HIV was God’s punishment for immorality, 96 (26.0%) believed it was curable, and 167(47.7%) said condom could prevent HIV and AIDS (Table 4). Most, 239 (68.3%) said they were HIV negative, and 12(3.4%) positive, 99(28.3%) did not know their status (Figure 1).

Table 1: Respondents’ sex, age, marital status and education

Variables	Number of respondents	Per cent
Sex		
Male	148	42.3%
Female	202	57.7%
Total	350	100.0%
Age		
15-19	78	22.5%
20-24	83	23.7%
25-29	69	19.7%
30-34	41	11.7%
35-39	24	6.8%
40-44	9	2.6%
45-49	12	3.4%
50-54	6	1.7%
55-59	9	2.6%
60-64	5	1.4%
65-69	11	3.1%
70 and above	3	0.8%
Total	350	100.0%

Marital status		
Single	192	54.8%
Married	111	31.7%
Divorced	14	4.0%
Separated	15	4.3%
Widowed	16	4.6%
Co-habitation	2	0.6%
Total	350	100.0%
Education		
No formal education	33	9.4%
Primary	30	8.6%
Secondary	190	54.2%
Tertiary	97	27.7%
Total	350	100.0%

Table 2: Occupation, Income, and Religion of Respondents.

Variables	Number of Respondents	Per cent
Occupation		
Farming	18	5.1%
Fishing	8	2.3%
Trading	63	18.0%
Student	121	34.6%
Civil Servant	89	25.5%
Artisan	11	3.1%
Unemployed	40	11.4%
Total	350	100.0%
Income per month		
N1,500-N5,000	36	10.3%
N6,000-N10,000	46	13.1%
N11,000-20,000	43	12.3%
N21,000 & above	65	18.6%
No income	158	45.1%
Total	350	100.0%
Religion		
Christian	315	90.0%
Muslims	20	5.7%
Traditional worshippers	15	4.3%
Total	350	100.0%

Table 3: Knowledge of HIV, source of information and mode of transmission

Variables	Number of respondents	Per cent
Awareness about HIV & AIDS		
Had heard about HIV and AIDS	345	98.6%
Had not heard about HIV and AIDS	5	1.4%
Total	350	100.0%
Reality about HIV & AIDS		
HIV & AIDS were real	331	94.5%
HIV & AIDS were not real	19	5.5%
Total	350	100.0%
Sources of information		*Multiple responses
Peer group	45	12.8%
Radio	196	56.0%
Television	92	26.3%
Newspaper	67	19.1%
Church	57	16.2%
Healthcare facility	67	22.8%
Parents	64	19.1%
Neighbours	64	18.2%

Knowledge of transmission	Yes	Per cent	No	Per cent
				*Multiple responses

Blood transfusion	326	93.1%	24	6.9%
Needle and syringe	321	91.7%	29	8.3%
Sharp objects	313	89.4%	37	10.6%
Mosquitoes	52	14.9%	298	85.1%
Witches and wizards	35	10.0%	315	90.0%
Kissing/hugging	70	20.0%	280	80.0%

Table 4: Beliefs about HIV and AIDS

Variables	Number of respondents	Per cent
Divine Involvement		
God's punishment for immorality	226	64.6%
Not God's punishment	124	35.4%
Total	350	100.0%
Curability		
AIDS has cure;	96	26.0%
AIDS has no cure	254	74.0%
Total	350	100.0%
Condom as means of prevention		
Condom prevents HIV and AIDS	167	47.7%
Condom does not prevent	183	52.3%
Total	350	100.0%

Sexual behaviour

Most respondents 315(90%) said they were sexually active, 35 (10.0%) never had sex. First sexual experience for 188(53.7%) was between 16 to 20 years, 94(26.9%) between 11 to 15 years, and 45(12.9%) 21 to 25 of years. Last sexual encounter for 185(52.9%) was with boy or girl friend, 116(33.1%) spouse, 31 (8.9%) concubine and commercial sex worker. A good proportion 182(52%) had one sexual partner, nearly half 168(48%) had more than one sexual partner (Table 5).

Reasons for one sexual partner was largely due to fear of sexually transmitted diseases 79 (53.3%) males and 81 (40.1%) females; satisfied with one partner 34(23.0%) males, 63(31.2%) females. Obviously, more females were satisfied with one sexual partner. Again, 60 (40.5%) males were not satisfied with one sexual partner and 66(32.7%) females; for pleasure 59 (39.9%) males and 59 (29.2%) females; unfaithfulness 23 (15.5%) males and 48 (23.7%) females. Similarly, reasons for using condoms during sex include avoiding sexually transmitted diseases 71 (48%) males and 55 (27.2%) females; avoiding unwanted pregnancy 15 (10.1%) males and 72 (35.6%) females; did not trust partner 56(37.85%) males and 58 (28.75%) females. Reasons for not using condom were: not pleasurable 92(62.1%) males, 49 (24.3%) females; married 29 (19.6%) males and 113(56.0%) females (Table 6).

Table 5: Age at first sex, last sex partner and number of partners

Variable	Number of respondents	Per cent
Sexually active	315	90.0%
Never had sex	35	10.0%
Total	350	100.0%
Age of first sex		
5-10 years	18	5.1%
11-15 years	94	26.9%
16-20 years	188	53.7%
21-25 years	45	12.9%
26 and above	5	1.4%
Total	350	100.0%
Last sex partner		
Spouse	116	33.1%
Concubine	31	8.9%
Boy/Girl friend	185	52.9%
Commercial sex worker	18	5.1%
Total	350	100.0%
Number of partners		
Had one sex partner	182	52.0%
Had more than one partner	168	48.0%
Total	350	100.0%

Table 6: Reasons for one or more partners, using and not using condom

Variables	Male(148)	Per cent	Female(202)	Per cent
Reasons for one partner				
Satisfied with one partner	34	23.0%	63	31.2%
Fear of sexually transmitted diseases	79	53.4%	81	40.1%
Faithfulness	11	7.4%	18	8.9%
Moral reasons	16	10.8%	20	9.9%
Marriage promise	8	5.4%	20	9.9%
Total	148	100%	202	100%
Reasons for more than one partner				
Not satisfied with one partner	60	40.5%	66	32.7%
Pleasure	59	39.9%	59	29.2%
Unfaithfulness	23	15.5%	48	23.7%
Partner refused sex	6	4.1%	29	14.4%
Total	148	100%	202	100%
Reasons for using condom				
Avoid STD	71	48.0%	55	27.2%
Avoid unwanted pregnancy	15	10.1%	72	35.6%
Did not trust partner	56	37.85	58	28.75
Media campaign	6	4.1%	17	8.5%
Total	148	100%	202	100%
Reasons for not using condom				
Not pleasurable	92	62.1%	49	24.3%
Married	29	19.6%	113	56.0%
Trust partner	9	6.1%	36	17.7%
Will not die alone	18	12.2%	4	2.0%
Total	148	100%	202	100%

Results from Respondents Living with HIV/AIDS

Demographic information

We administered questionnaire to fifty (50) members of the community living with HIV and AIDS receiving treatment at the general hospital who volunteered to participate in the study. Most 31(62.0%) were females and 19(38.0%) males, 11(22.0%) were 20 to 24 years, 10 (20.0%) 25 to 29 years, and 8(16.0%) 30-34 years. Nearly half 24(48.0%) were married, 14(28.0%) single, 6(12.0%) widowed and 4(8.0%) co-habited. Twenty (40.0%) had secondary education, 18(36.0%) primary, 7(14.0%) no formal education and 5 (10.0%) tertiary education. Occupation ranged from trading 11(22.0%) unemployed 10(20.0%) fishing 8(16.0%), farming 7(14.0%), and 4(8.0%) were students (Table 7). Large proportion 39 (78.0%) did not respond to the question on income, 4(8.0%) earned between N6, 000-N10, 000, 3(6.0%) N1, 500-N5, 000, and 2(4.0%) N11,000 - N21, 000. All respondents 50(100.0%) were Christians, 47 (94.0%) Nigerian, 33 (66.0 %) lived in the community 16 years or more and 9 (18.0%) less than one year (Table 8).

Table 7: Sex, age, marital status, education, and occupation of respondents

Characteristics	Number of respondents	Percentage
Sex		
Male	19	38.0%
Female	31	62.0%
Total	50	100.0%
Age		
15 – 19	2	4.0%
20 - 24	11	22.0%
25 – 29	10	20.0%
30 – 34	8	16.0%
35 – 39	4	8.0%
40 – 44	5	10.0%
45 – 49	5	10.0%
50 – 54	3	6.0%
55 – 59	0	0.0%
60 – 64	1	2.0%
65 – 69	1	2.0%
70 and above	0	0.0%
Total	50	100.0%
Marital Status		
Single	14	28.0%
Married	24	48.0%
Divorced	1	2.0%
Separated	1	2.0%
Widowed	6	12.0%
Co-habited	4	8.0%
Total	50	100.0%
Education		
No formal education	7	14.0%
Primary	18	36.0%
Secondary	20	40.0%
Tertiary	5	10.0%
Total	50	100.0%
Occupation		
Farming	7	14.0%
Fishing	8	16.0%
Trading	11	22.0%
Student	4	8.0%
Civil Servant	2	4.0%
Artisan	8	16.0%
Unemployed	10	20.0%
Total	50	100.0%

Table 8: Income, religion, years lived in the community

Variable	Number of respondents	Per cent
Monthly Income in Naira		
N 1,000 – N5,000	3	6.0%
N 6,000 – N10,000	4	8.0%
N 11,000 – N 20,000	2	4.0%
N 21,000 – above	2	4.0%
No response	39	78.0%
Total	50	100.0%
Religion		
Christianity	50	100.0%
Islam	0	0.0%
Traditional	0	0.0%
Total	50	100.0%
Years lived in the community		
Less than 1 year	9	18.0%
1 – 5 years	7	14.0%
6 – 10 years	1	2.0%
11 – 15 years	0	0.0%
16 years and above	33	66.0%
Total	50	100.0%
Nationality		
Nigerians	47	94.0%
Non – Nigerians	3	6.0%
Total	50	100.0%

Perception of illness and services

Most 44(88.0%) were diagnosed 1 to 3 years before the study 6(12.0%) 4 to 7 years. More than half 26 (52.0%) felt bad when diagnosed 9(18.0%) thought they had no future, 7(14.0%) felt like killing themselves, 6(12.0%) felt ashamed and 2(4.0%) felt stigmatised. However, many 36 (72.0 %) did not know if other members of their family were infected and 14(28.0%) knew other family members were infected (Table 9). Services available according to respondents were free anti retroviral drugs 37(74.0%), voluntary counselling and testing 32(64.0%) nutritional support 30 (60.0%), ante natal services 24 (48.0%) and post natal services 17(34.0%) (Table 10).

Table 9: Years since diagnosis, feeling at diagnosis, and family members status

Variables	Number of respondents	Per cent
Years since diagnosis		
1 – 3 years before study	44	88.0%
4 – 7 years before study	6	12.0%
Total	50	100.0%
Feeling at time of diagnosis		
Felt bad	26	52.0%
Had no future	9	18.0%
Felt like killing self	7	14.0%
Ashamed	6	12.0%
Stigmatized	2	4.0%
Total	50	100.0%
Status of family members		
Knew others were infected	14	28.0%
Did not know	36	72.0%
Total	50	100.0%

Table 10: Health care services available at the hospital *Multiple responses

Available Services	Number of respondents	Per cent
Voluntary Counselling & Testing	32	64.0%
Treatment preparation	3	6.0%
Free Antiretroviral Drugs	37	74.0%
Adherence Counselling	37	74.0%
Follow-up	31	62.0%
Antenatal Services	24	48.0%
Postnatal Services	17	34.0%
Nutritional Support	30	60.0%

Results show most respondents 46(92.0%) were satisfied with attitude of health care providers, and 41 (82.0 %) would not like to be cared for at another facility outside the environment, and 9(18.0%) would like to be cared for at another facility, largely due stigmatisation 25(50.0%), and shame 13 (26.0%) (Table 11). Very few felt access to the health facility was constrained 1(2.0%) due to lack of skilled personnel, 3(6.0%) access to health facilities/distance, 2(4.0%) unavailability of drugs, 1(2.0%) affordability (Table 12).

Compliance to treatment

All respondents were on antiretroviral drugs, most 43(86.0%) took their drugs regularly and 7(14.0%) did not. Reasons for not taking drugs regularly were side effects 23(46.0%), hunger 11(22.0%), forgetfulness 10(20.0%). Many 86.0 % (43) took their drugs twice daily while 7(14.0%) once daily. 41(82.0%) did not miss their dose, 5(10.0%) missed 1-3 times, 4(8.0%) missed 4-5 times. A good proportion 72(25) stopped taking their drug when experiencing difficulty, and 22(21.6) reported to care providers. Results show that 45 (90.0 %) kept their appointment with care providers, 24(48.0%) missed their appointment once, and 20(40.0%) missed more than three times (Table 13).

Table 11: Response to attitude of health care providers

Variables	Number of respondents	Per cent
Attitude of care providers		
Satisfied with attitude	46	92.0%
Not satisfied with attitude	4	8.0%
Total	50	100.0%
Facility Preference		
Preferred to be cared for at another facility	9	18.0%
Did not	41	82.0%
Total	50	100.0%
Reasons for preferring another facility		
Stigmatization	25	50.0%
Ashamed	13	26.0%
No response	12	24.0%
Total	50	100.0%

Table 12: Factors that affect utilization of services * Multiple responses

Factors	Yes	Per cent	No	Per cent
Attitude of healthcare providers	0	0%	47	94.0%
Lack of skill personnel	1	2%	46	92.0%
Accessing healthcare (distance)	3	6%	44	88.0%
Unavailability of drugs	2	4%	45	90.0%
Affordability of services	1	2%	46	92.0%
Lack of awareness	0	0	47	94.0%

Protection of partners

Results show 36(72.0) had support from family and 14(28.0%) did not. Most respondents 42(84.0%) faced challenges in the course of treatment and 8(16.0%) had no challenge. Types of challenges were side effects 13(26.0%), distance/accessibility, 8(16.0%) pill burden, and stigmatization (Table 14). Surprisingly, many respondents 19 (38.0%) did not protect their sexual partner, 12(24.0%) used condom, 14(28.0) gave no response, 5(10.0%) said they did not want to die alone (Table 15).

Table 13: Compliance to Treatment

Variables	Number of respondents	Per cent
Took drugs regularly	43	86.0%
Did not take drugs regularly	7	14.0%
Total	50	100
Reasons for not taking drugs regularly		
Side-effects	23	46.0%
Hunger	11	22.0%
Forgetfulness	10	20.0%
Did not understand advice of health workers	4	8.0%
Travelled	2	4.0%
Total	50	100.0%
Number of times a day drug was taken		
Once daily	7	14.0%

Twice daily	43	86.0%
Total	50	100.0%
Number of times drug was missed		
None	41	82.0%
1-3	5	10.0%
4-7	4	8.0%
Total	50	100.0%
When Experiencing difficulty		
Stopped taking drugs	36	72%
Reported to health workers	11	22%
Went to church	3	0.6%
Total	50	100%
Appointment		
Kept their appointments	45	90.0%
Did not keep appointment	5	10.0%
Total	50	100.0%
Number missed in the last one year		
Once	24	48.0%
Twice	2	4.0%
Three times	4	8.0%
More than three times	20	40.0%
Total	50	100.0%

Table 14: Family Support and Challenges Faced by Respondents

Variables	Number of respondents	Percentages
Support from family		
Received support from family	36	72.0%
Did not get support from family	14	28.0%
Total	50	100.0%
Faced challenge in the course of taking ARV	42	84.0%
No challenge	8	16.0%
Total	50	100.0%
Type of challenge * Multiple responses		
Stigmatization	1	2.0%
Side Effects	13	26.0%
Pill burden	8	16.0%
Distance/Accessibility	13	26.0%
Affordability	3	6.0%
Forgetfulness	2	4.0%

Table 15: Protection of Sexual Partner

Responses	Number of respondents	Per cent
No protection	19	38.0%
Use of condom	12	24.0%
Will not die alone	5	10.0%
No response	14	28.0%
Total	50	100.0%

DISCUSSION

HIV prevalence in Iquita community has remained higher than even urban communities in Nigeria, indeed one of few rural communities with rates higher than urban areas. This is worrisome; this study was therefore to understand factors that could potentially be contributing to the spread of HIV in the community. HIV thrives in an environment that enables it to do so, in view of economic, cultural, social, and political circumstances (WHO 2005). Results show that knowledge about transmission was high in the population 326(93.1%) said through blood transfusion, 321(91.7%) needle and syringes, 317(90.6%) unprotected sex, 313(89.4%) said sharp objects. Yet 20.0% said kissing/hugging 14.9% mosquitoes, 10.0% witches, and wizards, and 64.6% believed HIV was God's punishment for immorality.

Although 68.3% said they were HIV negative, and 3.4% positive, 28.3% did not know their status in such an environment and with knowledge of HIV and AIDS, 90% was sexually active, and early onset of sexual activity early. Last sexual encounter for 52.9% was with boy or girl friend, and 8.9% concubine and commercial sex worker, nearly 50% had more than one sexual partner; 40.5% males and 32.7% females were not satisfied with one sexual partner, yet many did not like using

condom because it was pleasurable 62.1% males and 24.3% females; and 19.6% males and 56.0% females said because they were married.

Furthermore, results from the 50 members of the community living with HIV, receiving treatment, and counselling show that 72.0 % did not know if other members of their family were infected; 38.0% did not protect their sexual partner, only 24.0% used condom, 28.0% gave no response, and 10.0% said they were not going to die alone. This means that despite the treatment, counselling, and knowledge of HIV transmission some respondents presumably did set out to infect others in the population by not taking measures to protect partners.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, results of this study suggest numerous factors potentially contributing to persistent high prevalence HIV in Iquita, particularly multiple sexual partners, and reluctance to use condom. In-depth qualitative research is required for deeper understanding of the persistent high HIV prevalence in this rural community, and behaviour of people living with HIV.

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Received for Publication: 25/02/2012

Accepted for Publication: 13/04/2012

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